

Impact of Smartphone Addiction on Adjustment of Secondary Students

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Abstract

The present study was conducted to find out the impact of Smartphone Addiction on different aspects of Adjustment as Emotional, Social and Educational Adjustment. After studying the previous researches on Smartphone Addiction, school Adjustment and Self control, it was found that result of these studies was not clearly demonstrated as per requirement. The current study is focused on the association between Smartphone Addiction and different aspects of Adjustment. For this purpose Researcher used Dr. Vijayshri and Dr. Masaud Ansari Smartphone Addiction Scale (SAS) and Dr. AKP Sinha and Dr. R. P. Sinha Adjustment Inventory to collect the data for present study. For analyzing the data of present study, Researcher used Karl Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient Method. Total sample comprising 60 secondary students from Saharanpur district was selected. The result of the Study shows a positive relationship between variables, as Smartphone Addiction increase need of Adjustment also tends to be increase.

Keywords: Smartphone Addiction, Adjustment, Emotional Adjustment, Social Adjustment and Education Adjustment.

Introduction

"Technology is not just a tool – it's a reflection of human imagination, turning ideas into reality and reshaping the world with every innovation." Smartphone is also an innovation like this. Smartphone features and connectivity is evolving day by day. Smartphone can be addressed as a cause of tech revolution. But increasing dependency and overuse of Smartphone is a sign of its 'Addiction'. **Y S Lee (2006)**, defined Addiction as it is not only related to drug or substance abuse, but it also used to gambling, internet, games or even Smartphone. Smartphone become more popular when Apple's I-phone was addressed in 2007, with more customer friendly and updated features like touch screen interface and a virtual keyboard. '**New Time Mobility Poll**' reported that 84% people couldn't go a single day without their mobile (by **New York Daily News 2019**).

In **2020**, the percentage of Smartphone users reached to a standing 54% in comparison to only 22% of mobile users were using Smartphone in 2016. According to a report by 2040, the figure is supposed to reach 96% which is not surprising as the volume of shipments of Smartphone to India was around 149.7 million pieces in 2020 itself. In current scenario use of Smartphone is adversely increasing. We can understand the concept of Adjustment with **Charles Darwin (1869)** theory, 'Survival of fittest'. This theory explain about the struggle to survive on the earth. In this process of struggle one can be disappointed and other can be excited to strike the balance between his urges and life situations. The person who can turn hard situations into new opportunities can be said adjusted and the process used by him can be called Adjustment. "A good Adjustment is one which is both realistic and satisfying. At least in the long run, it reduces to the minimum the Frustrations, the tensions, and anxieties which a person must endure. It provides an evenness of satisfaction of the whole person, rather than the Satisfaction of the one intense drive at the expense of others (Smith 1961)."

Mahrooqi, et al. (2020) conducted a study to find the relationship between Smartphone Addiction and Depression. The result revealed a high level Smartphone Addiction based on SAS-SV scores. It was found that there is a significant positive correlation between Smartphone Addiction and Depression scores. **Bhanderi, et al. (2021)** also conducted a study to explore Smartphone Addiction among the Adolescents. The result of study revealed that Smartphone use was associated with age, residential area, parent's education and income. Smartphone Addiction found significantly higher in urban Adolescents in comparison to rural Adolescents. One more study was conducted by **Heo & Lee (2018)** on Smartphone Addiction and Adjustment among higher secondary students. But the result was not clearly illustrated. But the result of this study can be helpful in developing programs to improve Adjustment among higher secondary students.

Significance of the Study

The Researcher conducted this study to find out the significant impact of Smartphone addition on Adjustment of learner. The study will try to put light on the Smartphone use and Addiction which influence the secondary student's Adjustment. Smartphone use and its Addiction are two different aspects that influence the Adjustment of students. Smartphone use under proper mentorship can yield positive results and Smartphone Addiction can cause turbulence in life of an individual both mentally and physically through this study is a sincere effort has been made and isolates Smartphone Addiction in secondary student's life and creating an awareness of its severity. Future implications of this study will help teachers to help students to use their phone smartly for personal & other educational purposes.

Statement of the problem : "Impact of Smartphone Addiction on Adjustment of Secondary Students."

Objectives

- To study the relationship between Smartphone Addiction and Adjustment of Secondary Students.
- To study the relationship between Smartphone Addiction and Emotional Adjustment of Secondary Students.
- To study the relationship between Smartphone Addiction and Social Adjustment of Secondary Students.
- To study the relationship between Smartphone Addiction and Educational Adjustment of Secondary Students.

Hypotheses

- There is no significant relationship between Smartphone Addiction and Adjustment of Secondary Students.
- There is no significant relationship between Smartphone Addiction and Emotional Adjustment of Secondary Students.
- There is no significant relationship between Smartphone Addiction and Social Adjustment of Secondary Students.
- There is no significant relationship between Smartphone Addiction and Educational Adjustment of Secondary Students.

Research Methodology: Descriptive survey research method has been applied to demonstrate the result of this study.

Sample of the Study: A sample comprising of 60 Secondary level Students was randomly selected from various UP Board Secondary Schools in Saharanpur district.

Psychological tools

(I) SAS - Smartphone Addiction Scale : This scale was developed by Dr. Vijayshri and Dr. Masaud Ansari. SAS is based on five point Likert scale. It is based on self reporting. This scale has 23 items divided into six dimensions as Compulsion, Forgetfulness, Lack of attention, Depression and Anxiety, Disturbed hunger/sleep and Social withdrawal.

(II) **Adjustment Inventory** : Adjustment Inventory is developed by Dr. AKP Sinha and Dr. R.P. Sinha. It consisted 3 areas of Adjustment and 60 items in format of questionnaire with yes or no response. In this inventory questionnaire result with high marks shows lack of Adjustment vice versa.

Statistical Technique used: Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used for present study.

Variables

Independent variable: Smartphone Addiction.

Dependent variable: Adjustment.

Statistical Tool: Researcher used appropriate statistical technique to analyze the collected data of the study.

Result and Interpretation

Table-1
Correlation Coefficient between Smartphone Addiction and Adjustment

Variables	N	Correlation Coefficient	df	Level of significance
1. Smartphone Addiction	60	+0.1996	58	Not significant
2. Total Adjustment				

Table shows that calculated value of Correlation Coefficient between Smartphone Addiction and Adjustment of secondary students +0.1996 is less than the tabulated value 0.250, at 0.05 level of significance. Thus result shows a positive correlation between them. Hence null hypothesis (Ho) is accepted here which states that Smartphone Addiction and Adjustment has no significant relationship. Although both the variables are related to each other but not strongly. The positive sign (+) suggests that as Smartphone Addiction increases, need of Adjustment also tends to increase but not strongly.

Table-2
Correlation Coefficient between Smartphone Addiction and Emotional Adjustment

Variables	N	Correlation Coefficient	df	Level of Significance
1. Smartphone Addiction	60	+0.3297	58	Significant
2. Emotional Adjustment				

Table shows that calculated value of Correlation Coefficient between Smartphone Addiction and Emotional Adjustment of secondary students +0.3297 is greater than the tabulated value 0.250, at 0.05 level of significance. Hence null hypothesis (Ho) is rejected by researcher which states that Smartphone Addiction and Emotional Adjustment has no significant relationship. The result shows a moderate level positive correlation between the given variables.

This shows that individuals who has higher levels of Smartphone Addiction, they tend to experience greater difficulties in Emotional Adjustment. However, the strength of this correlation is not strong, implying that while Smartphone Addiction may contribute to Emotional Adjustment issues, other factors likely influence emotional well – being as well.

Table-3
Correlation Coefficient between Smartphone Addiction and Social Adjustment

Variables	N	Correlation Coefficient	df	Level of significance
1. Smartphone Addiction	60	-0.1272	58	Not significant
2. Social Adjustment				

Table shows that calculated value of Correlation Coefficient between Smartphone Addiction and Social Adjustment of secondary students -0.1272 is less than the tabulated value 0.250, at 0.05 level of significance, shows a **negative** correlation. Hence, null hypothesis (Ho) is accepted here which states that Smartphone Addiction and Social Adjustment of secondary students has no significant

relationship. Since the value is **negative**, it indicates that as Smartphone Addiction increases, Social Adjustment tend to improve slightly, or vice versa. It shows that students are Socially active on internet and Social media. Such a low correlation suggests that Smartphone Addiction and Social Adjustment are almost independent or have minimal association.

Table-4
Correlation Coefficient between Smartphone Addiction and Educational Adjustment

Variables	N	Correlation Coefficient	df	Level of significance
1.Smartphone Addiction	60	+0.1556	58	Not significant
2. Educational Adjustment				

Table shows that calculated value of Correlation Coefficient between Smartphone Addiction and Educational Adjustment of secondary students +0.1556 is less than the tabulated value 0.250 at 0.05 level of significance. The result of study shows a weak positive correlation. Hence, null hypothesis (Ho) is accepted here which states that Smartphone Addiction and Educational Adjustment of secondary students has no significant relationship. Since the correlation is positive, students with higher Smartphone Addiction may face slightly more difficulties in adjusting academically, but other factors are likely contributing more significantly.

Conclusion

After analyzing the data of present study we can conclude that Smartphone Addiction increases, need of all aspects of Adjustment also tends to increase, but not strongly. Although we found that students being socially active on internet are more socially adjusted as we found negative value of correlation between Smartphone Addiction and Social Adjustment. After analyzing the data we found that there is a difference between Smartphone Addiction of male and female secondary students as their mean is 79.37 for male and 57.3 is for female students. This shows that male student spend more time with their Smartphone in comparison to female students. Like this Adjustment data was also analyzed by researcher on the basis of gender. But not a big difference was found in Adjustment of male and female secondary students. This study suggests that secondary students should use Smartphone under the guidance or mentorship of parents or teacher. If students use Smartphone under guidance and smartly, it can be helpful in all areas of Adjustment and life situations.

Suggestions

Although Smartphone Addiction may contribute to difficulties in Adjustment, other factors likely play a big role in adjustment . The weak correlation suggests that Smartphone Addiction alone is not a strong predictor of Adjustment. For further studies Researcher should analyze additional variables or use multivariate analysis to see if the relationship changes when controlling other factors. Other factors (e. g; environment, psychological aspects, family, lifestyle habits) may influence Smartphone Addiction as well Adjustment strongly. Thus Smartphone Addiction impact on Adjustment is negative but for further studies we should include more variables to study.

Reference

1. **Boumosleh Jocelyne & Jaalouk Doris (2018)** Smartphone Addiction among University Students and Its Relationship with Academic Performance. *Global Journal of Health Science*. Vol.10, No.1
2. **Bukhori Baidi, et.al. (2019)** The Effect of Smartphone Addiction, achievement Motivation, and Textbook Reading Intensity on Students' academic Achievement. *International Journal of Interactive Mobile Technologies*. Vol. 13, No.09.
3. **Cha Soo-Seong & Seo Kyung-Bo (2018)** Smartphone use and Smartphone Addiction in Middle school students in Korea: Prevalence, Social networking service, and Game use. *Sage Journals*, <https://doi.org/10.1177/2055102918755046>
4. **Daoud Rana, et.al. (2020)** The educational value of internet use in the home for school Children: A systematic review of literature. *Journal of Research on Technology in Education*. Pages- 353-374, Vol 53, Issue-4 DOI: 10.1080/15391523.2020.1783402

5. **Davey Sanjeev & Davey Anuradha (2014)** Assessment of Smartphone Addiction in Indian adolescents: A Mixed Method Study by Systematic Review and Meta-analysis Approach. International Journal of Preventive Medicine 5(12): 1500-11
6. **Devi, Madhusmita (2016)** Mobile Phone Addiction among undergraduate college Students of Guwahati Metropolitan Area: A Study, International Journal of Research in Social Sciences, Vol. 6, 470-480.
7. **Domoff E. Sarah, et.al (2019)** Addictive Phone use and academic Performance in Adolescents, Human Behavior and Emerging Technologies/ Volume 2, Issue1/p.33-38
8. **El-Badawa. A. and Hashem Yasmin (2015)** the Impact of Social Media on the Academic Development of School Students. International Journal of Business Administration, Vol.6. No.1
9. **Emeka, Jeremiah Ugwulebo & Nyeche Sunday Okoro, b(2016)** A Study on the impact Of internet usage on the Academic Performance of Undergraduates Students: A Case Study, International Journal of Scientific and Engineering Research, Vol.7, Issue 10, ISSN 2229, 5518
10. <https://www.risingkashmir.com/Smartphone-Addiction--Dark-Sides-of-theMagical-Device-81627>
11. <https://www.psychguides.com/behavioral-disorders/cell-phone-Addiction/signs-and-symptoms/ Control>
12. <https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Smartphone>
13. https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Addiction_psychology
14. <https://www.elitemv.com/2019/09/target-population-differs-from.html?m=1>
15. New York times daily news report (2019).

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